

AMOC Observation as Critical Infrastructure

Summary & Key Recommendations

POLICY BRIEFING

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Summary for policymakers

This document presents a summary for policy makers from the report **“AMOC Observation as Critical Infrastructure. Overview & Recommendations for Nordic Ministers”**. The full report is available online.

The report is offered as a contribution to Nordic ministerial deliberations in 2026 and to the European institutional processes now under way through the Ocean Pact, the forthcoming Ocean Act, and the OceanEye initiative.

Sustained observation is foundational to any government strategy on AMOC risk: it is what monitors the evolution of the system, on which any wider response depends.

A shutdown of operations in key AMOC observation systems would most likely take years to restart, resulting not only in loss of the analytical capability the record was building, but in loss of our ability to detect weakening trends for decades to come — with direct consequences for Nordic capacity to plan, prepare, and act on AMOC risk.

A fundamental shift in mentality is required. A wait-and-see posture at this time could have drastic consequences. The current observation system was never designed for a world of AMOC security relevance, and while heroically held together by scientists over the years, it is at the brink of collapse for key components. The required shift has two elements: immediate action to secure the components already in place, and political recognition of AMOC observation as critical infrastructure to Nordic security — with an eye towards expansion to fit-for-purpose status.

Two components of the AMOC observing system are in Critical condition, with material exposure on an eighteen-month horizon: the RAPID array at 26.5°N (continuous since 2004, the longest transbasin record) and OSNAP in the subpolar North Atlantic. A further set of systems are at risk on a known timeline, typically 2026–2028: MOVE, SAMBA, Davis Strait, the global Argo programme, and the GO-SHIP global hydrographic programme. RAPID and OSNAP are further exposed to Argo and GO-SHIP, on which they depend to calculate transport.

OSNAP, the most extensive basin-wide AMOC array, is a five-country (US, UK, DE, NL, CA) co-dependency in which failure of any single national contribution risks ending the observation. The United States contributes approximately half through competitive grants now exposed to FY2027 federal budget proposals. The United Kingdom contributes through National Capability funding subject to year-on-year reductions, placing UK contributions at material risk from 2027. The Netherlands contributes through moorings sustained over twelve years by a single principal investigator through consecutive open-competition grants, with post-2028 prospects highly uncertain.

Nordic gateway monitoring — across the Greenland–Scotland Ridge, the Norwegian Sea, and the Arctic gateways — sits in a different exposure category. Funding flows through institutional appropriations, but is not ring-fenced for observation and is vulnerable to fiscal compression.

The Nordic Countries together hold the most operationally significant AMOC observing assets outside the basin-wide arrays. The Greenland–Scotland Ridge monitoring currently consists of a collection of distinct national arrays rather than a coherent observing system. Closing remaining gaps and integrating these arrays would produce a trans-basin measurement, comparable in scientific weight to the RAPID and OSNAP arrays.

Iceland's government has designated AMOC collapse as a national security threat; Finland's Strategic Task 37 framework recognises AMOC collapse as a critical tipping point for national security and economic planning. The fate of the AMOC observing system — whether operated from within or outside the Nordic Countries — therefore falls within the legitimate scope of Nordic ministerial action. Two European processes in 2026 will shape how AMOC observation is embedded in European ocean-observation architecture for the coming decade: the EU Ocean Act and the OceanEye initiative, with its pledging event in September 2026.

Interested to learn more?

Access the full report **“AMOC Observation as Critical Infrastructure. Overview & Recommendations for Nordic Ministers”**.

Recommendations for Nordic Ministers

Recommendation 1.

Engage directly, individually and collectively, with the governments whose decisions most determine the fate of critical AMOC observing components — principally the United Kingdom, the Netherlands and the United States.

Recommendation 2.

Articulate a coordinated Nordic position on AMOC observations, and pledge existing Nordic funded contributions, within the EU Ocean Act and OceanEye processes during 2026.

Recommendation 3.

Establish a standing Nordic Council of Ministers coordination group on AMOC observation with a provisional multi-year mandate, oriented toward the broader trans-Atlantic observing partnership, as the counterpart through which the recommendations below are commissioned.

Recommendation 4.

Commission the standing group to prepare backstop arrangements for the 2026–2028 funding transition, covering both emergency funding mechanisms ready for ministerial activation and operational support arrangements through which Nordic ship-time and observational capacity can be contributed to externally-operated programmes.

Recommendation 5.

Commission the standing group to scope a coordinated Nordic Seas AMOC observing system, including complete trans-basin measurement of overturning across the GSR, funded through a dedicated Nordic Council of Ministers line.

Recommendation 6.

Pursue national critical-infrastructure designation for Nordic observing assets, in line with the framing the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission and the European Ocean Pact have adopted for ocean observation more broadly.